

Temperance Activism in the Anti-Colonial Movement in Karnataka

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The imperialist policy of the British had resulted in fragmentation of the Kannada provinces into 22 administrative units. Of these various units, the largest Kannada speaking population was found in the State of Mysore. While Marathi was predominant in the Bombay-Karnataka regions Telugu and to some extent Tamil in Madras – Karnataka. Since the division in the administration had been done to suit the convenience of the imperial policy, it was difficult to forge a common front of Kannadigas in the context of nationalism. Bombay and Poona were the centers of intense nationalistic activities and the students from Kannada regions who went there for higher education were naturally drawn into the nationalistic current. In the above said circumstances one has to study the nationalistic activities in Kannada provinces. In the present study an attempt is made here to study temperance movement in Kannada provinces.

Early years Abkari in Mysore

Abkari.—This branch of revenue was formerly known in Mysore under the name of Panch Bab, or the five items," namely, toddy, arrack, ganja, betel-leaf and tobacco. The two last were transferred, the former in 1838-9, and the latter in 1850-1, to the head of Sayer. Up to 1862 the manufacture of toddy, arrack, and ganja was under the direct management of Government. In that year the Abkari revenue, including these three items, was temporarily farmed to contractors, prior to the introduction of the Sadar Distillery system, which came into operation in 1863-4 ; but it was not till 1865-6 that steps could be taken to carry its principles fully into effect in the removal of all obstructions to open competition in the manufacture of spirits. The system referred to provides for the erection of a large enclosure, styled a Sadar Distillery, at the head quarters of each District (and in other places, if the consumption requires it), in which all country spirits consumed in the District must be manufactured. Any person duly licensed may erect a still, at his own expense, within the enclosure, and distil as much liquor as he pleases, removing it himself, or selling it to the licensed vendors, on the sole condition that before removal the excise duty must be paid,

and the liquor reduced to the authorized strength, the officers of Government confining themselves to taking such precautions as will insure no liquor being passed out of the ABKARI distillery except on these conditions, and having nothing to do with the manufacture, or the price at which the produce is sold. The object was to secure for the consumer a superior quality of spirit, of standard strength, tested at the Government distilleries within the precincts of which it is manufactured, and to which it pays a still-head duty before removal. A restricted system of licenses for the sale of the liquor, combined with regulations for the supervision of the vendors, also tended to check the promiscuous establishment of shops. The sale of fermented toddy, the liquor commonly used by the lower classes, was also subject to the license regulations. But only the arrack portion of the Abkari revenue was worked under the Sadar Distillery system. The items of toddy and ganja were farmed out to contractors. In 1874 a general revision was made of the rates of still-head duty, which varied in different parts from 14 annas to Rs. 3, and they were raised to Rs. 2 per gallon throughout the Province, excepting in the towns of Bangalore and Mysore, in which the rates were fixed at Rs. 3 and 2 respectively. The strength of the liquor to be issued from the distilleries was fixed at 190 below proof. But in 1875 a special arrangement for 3 years was made for the Mysore District with the Ashtagram Sugar Works at Palhalli, by which the Company contracted to manufacture liquor at 200 under proof and sell it to Government at 13 Annas per gallon. The liquor was sold to vendors on the spot at Rs. 4 per gallon when intended for consumption in the town of Mysore, and at Rs. 3 for consumption elsewhere within the District. The retail vendors were bound to sell to the public within the town of Mysore at Rs. 5 per gallon, and beyond the town at Rs. 4 per Liter. The following figures will show the immediate operation of the new rules on the sale and consumption of arrack. License fees in Bangalore transferred to Municipality. + System of putting up retail shops to auction discontinued. 1. Inimdars whose sannads included the right, received the revenue from arrack licenses in their Inam villages.

Administration

In 1878-9 the Sadar Distillery system was discontinued in the Nandidroog Division, the exclusive right of manufacturing and selling arrack being given out on contract for 3 years. The brewing of beer, at 3 breweries in operation in Bangalore, rapidly increased. A still-head duty of 2 annas a gallon was imposed on it in 1873-4, and the number of gallons brewed rose from 58,000 in that year to 140,000 in 1875-6, but the production afterwards fell off considerably. From April 1876 the still-head duty was raised to 4 annas per gallon, but from March 1879 it was again reduced to 2 annas. Toddy in this Province is extracted from date-trees, which grow wild throughout the country, and in a few places from cocoanut and sago-palm trees. All date-trees growing on Government or ryotwarilands, whether occupied or unoccupied, are regarded as at the disposal of Government for Abkari purposes; but trees growing on occupied Government lands in the surveyed taluqs, and those in inam and kayam gutta villages the toddy revenue of which is granted to the holders by their sanads, are regarded as the property of the land-holder, and are therefore excluded from the contractor's lease. The exclusive right of drawing and vending the toddy was rented out to the contractors for a term, which varied in the different Divisions. The area over which such right might be exercised varied from one taluq to a District, according to the circumstances of the District and means of the contractor. Till 1872 the farming of the toddy was leased out annually in Nandidroog and Ashtagram, and for five years in Nagar, but owing to the inconvenience of frequently changing contractors, the latter period was adopted in all. Date reserves are being formed in each District on waste or unoccupied lands, demarcated for the purpose as the survey progresses. This measure is necessary to guard against the possible inconvenience of a general destruction of date-trees on their kandyam lands by the ryots. No grant of land for cultivation is made within the limits of such

reserves. The revenue derived from a tax on spirituous liquors, ganja and toddy, appears from the accounts of 1799- 1800, to have produced Kanthiraya pagodas 28,800, or Rs. 84,000 in that year, and Kanthiraya pagodas 44,290, or Rs. 1,29,179 in 1802-3. The receipts are not distinctly shown in the earlier years of British Administration, but in the accounts of 1836-7, the Abkari revenue is entered at 2½ lakhs of rupees, and it gradually rose, producing 10½ lakhs in 1872-3. The next two years it was 11½ lakhs, and in 1875-6 reached 12½ lakhs. Owing to the famine it then diminished every year till in 1879-80 it was only 8.64 lakhs. In 1880-1 it began to revive and stood at 10.67 lakhs. Heads of Departments were appointed for Forests and Police in 1885, for Excise in 1889.

Anti-Liquor agitation in British India actually started with the emergence of extremist nationalism. In early 1880's Lokamanya Tilak raised his voice against the excise policy of the colonial government. Lokamanya Tilak while writing on the evil of liquor in his well known news paper *Mahratta* wrote : "The reckless encouragement of the vice of drunkenness, is the most serious charge that can be laid against the government That the vice of drunkenness is daily and yearly increasing to a serious extent is a fact which also derives strong corroboration from the marvelous increase of the revenue from excise during the last eight years. From the year 1871-72 to 74-75, the revenue from excise was nearly the same amounting to Rs. 2,40,00,000 annually. From that year it has steadily increased till it amounted to about 3,60,00,000 in the last official year. Thus, during these eight years the revenue has increased under this head by 1,20,00,000. It cannot be doubted that a large portion of this increased revenue is derived from the liquor traffic. If we now take into account the sum spent by the government on the education of the people we shall find that government does not spend even as much on this account as it derives from the ever increasing sale of liquor and the consequent demoralization of the people; for in the last year government spent only Rs. 1,13,39,000 and this is the largest sum spent by the government upto this time on the education of the people they rule". Later the spirit of anti-liquor agitation continued.

On August 20th, 1907, the Poona Temperance Association (PTA) was formed. G.K. Gokhale, was elected to the chair of the organization, aided by other leaders like Lokamanya Tilak, N.C. Kelkar, and the missionary, A. Robinson. The main object of the organization was to "educate public opinion and to secure a more restrictive administration of abkari laws." The PTA was a coalition of Congressmen of both "extremist" and moderates. Beginning on April 2nd, 1908, temperance volunteers began to picket liquor shops in Poona under the auspices of the PTA. The picketing was remarkably effective and liquor shops that once sold as much as 25-30 gallons per day saw their sales plummet to a mere one or two gallons. The British Abkari Policy was strongly criticized by Rangacharlu, the first Dewan of Mysore after rendition as early as 1881. In his book, "50 years of British Administration in Mysore", Rangacharlu criticized the Abkari Policy of the colonial government. In the early 1890's, the native nationalistic news papers like *Karnataka Prakashika* raised its voice against the consumption of liquor. Most of the early nationalists in Karnataka were strong followers of Lokamanya Tilak politically. Naturally they followed the model of Poona.

During the Swadeshi movement, as a part of the Boycott, a liquor ban was observed by the local leaders. Leaders like Alur Venkata Rao, Gangadhara Rao Deshpande and Madhva Rao Kabbur led the movement. The first boycott was held at Dharwar in 1908. Kannada news papers did not lag behind in spreading the message against the consumption of liquor and the practice of temperance. During the Non-co operation movement, the temperance activism and picketing were more popular in the Kannada provinces. The national leadership combined both Khilafat and Non-Cooperation Movement. Naturally, both Hindu and Muslims participated in the movement. The activists first tried to persuade the drinkers. In some areas, drinkers were fined with a penalty. In many areas drinkers were paraded in public seated on a donkey. Fine collected from drinkers was sent to the Khilafat Fund. Attacking toddy forests and destroying it was also seen during this period. The tour of Mahatma Gandhi and Shaikat Ali to Dharwad and Haveri inspired many people to join the temperance movement. The most important event during Non Co operation Movement was

the picketing at Dharwad which finally ended with a golibar(firing) and the death of three people. During this Non Cooperation Movement, the picketing was carried out throughout the state. Along with Hindi Prachar, Hindu-Muslim Unity and temperance was also given prominence during the movement. News papers like Mysore Star, Sadhvi, Karnataka, Swdeshabhimani played a major role in carrying the message of temperance.

In 1924, during the Congress session of Belgaum which was presided over by Mahatma Gandhi, Dr. N.S. Hardikar formed 'Hindustni Seva Dal' a auxiliary organization of the INC. The volunteers of the Sevadals worked hard in carrying out the message of Mahatma Gandhi. During Sevadals camps, volunteers were trained. Special attention was given towards picketing. Later when the Civil Disobedience Movement was started, these Sevadals volunteers played a major role in picketing. Women volunteers like Uma bai Kundapur, Krishna Bai Panjekar, Bellary Siddamma and a host of others actively participated in picketing of liquor shops and attacks on toddy forests. During this period, Jangal Satyagraha and Forest Satyagraha was carried out in Tiruvannur, Hecce, Tigane, Hekunja and other places where thousands were arrested and were sentenced to imprisonment. All most all the taluks of Mysore province witnessed the activity of picketing. In a rare incident, a 18 year girl Kolara Kaveri committed suicide because she was not permitted to participate in picketing by her parents. This enormous response of the people led to fall of Abkari income of the state which is evident from the statistics given below.

Table showing the Excise Revenue of Mysore (In Rupees)

Year	Arrack	Toddy	Ganja	Total
1904-05	19,93,950	17,62,327	42,508	
1905-06	18,68,003	19,30,597	53,362	
1929-30	29,41,913	40,05,182	4,28,329	
1930-31	26,95,288	39,48,922	4,03,723	
1931-32	21,77,936	31,98,497	3,79,603	
1932-33	2,10,334	32,56,206	4,04,813	
1933-34	19,60,827	32,43,051	4,19,330	
1934-35	17,86,896	31,43,051	4,20,454	
1935-36	16,99,009	31,60,849	39,067	
1936-37	16,20,708	31,30,659	3,92,616	
1937-38	16,79,030	32,30,993	4,18,467	
1938-39	16,29,034	31,87,978	4,27,412	
1939-40	16,01,801	34,23,196	3,91,235	

On the other hand, Mysore government also tried to advocate the temperance. Some days in a month particularly on salary day were declared as 'Dry Day' on which the sale of liquor was banned. In industrial areas like Bangalore, Mysore, Mandya, Kolar, Davanagere and Chitradurga special attention was given to educate the industrial laborers regarding the temperance. Meanwhile the literary field also did not lag behind in responding to the developments. Contemporary writers like Ta. Ra. Subba Rao, Aa. na. Krishna Rao, Gorur Ramaswami Iyengar (who were also freedom fighters) wrote novels on such themes. Novels like Rakta Tarpana, Meravanige can be mentioned here. A good no. of ballads, folk songs and even lullabies were composed in this regard. As concluding remarks, it can be said that Karnataka played a major role in anti-liquor movement. Starting with the extremist era the temperance activity continued in Gandhian era.

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